

PROOF OF CONTEXTS

*New accessibility
for archive users*

Final report

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15 April 2025

Contents

Introduction	3
Chapter 1: The ideas.....	5
Helping the Filing Monster	5
From tree to network.....	8
Chapter 2: How? The implementation	12
Example: starting by hand	12
In the future: automated.....	16
Chapter 3: The design.....	17
The route	17
The prototypes.....	17
Chapter 4: The responses.....	25
Interim presentation to archivists from the province of Noord-Holland	25
Interim presentation to the members of the Noord-Holland Archivists' Circle	26
User study	26
Conclusion and next steps.....	28
Next steps	28
Points requiring attention	29
With our thanks to	31
Photo report	32

Title page image:

'User experience'. Andy, Terry and Jill arrive on an island filled with stacks of filing cabinets. Andy Griffiths and Terry Denton, *The 117-Storey Treehouse* (Macmillan children's books, London, 2019) 236-237.

This report was previously published in Dutch:

Merel Geerling and Nico Vriend, *Proof of Context: een nieuwe toegankelijkheid voor archiefgebruikers*, 9

December 2024. Accessible at: <https://noord->

[hollandsarchief.nl/images/Projecten/Proof_of_Contexts_Eindrapport.pdf](https://noord-hollandsarchief.nl/images/Projecten/Proof_of_Contexts_Eindrapport.pdf)

Introduction

Imagine you're suffering from a toothache. You want the problem to be solved quickly, so you make an appointment with the dentist. What do you expect to encounter when you get there? Certainly a trained practitioner, a modern surgery and sterile instruments. But once you're sitting in the treatment chair, the dentist approaches you with a rusty old pair of pliers. "Don't worry," says the dentist, "I always do it this way and it always turns out perfectly." What would you do? You would probably get up, run out of the building and think to yourself: I'm never coming back here again!

'Pulling teeth', 26 February 1963. De Boer press photo agency, Noord-Holland Archives

Thankfully no dentist works like that today. Dentists use the latest medical techniques and are trained to apply them as effectively as possible. You can count on that.

This report isn't about the user experience at the dentist, but when using archives. How do users experience archives when they come to look for information? In this case, too, people have a need: to find certain information. They go to the right place – the archives – and expect to be able to find that information quickly and efficiently. However, what they currently encounter is the equivalent of those rusty old pliers: users are referred to an online archive inventory, with a structure and jargon that many people find incomprehensible. It's no surprise that new users often leave, probably never to return...

Don't get us wrong: as an instrument to make archives accessible, the inventory has worked well for decades. Just as patients were happy to have painful, rotting teeth pulled, even with pliers, before the advent of modern dentistry, researchers were also satisfied with the archive inventory for many years. After all, it wasn't necessary to plough through reams of paper to – eventually – find what you

were looking for. However, the idea that archives are inherently ‘difficult’, and that ‘people must do their best to learn to use them’ is outdated. To guarantee their future relevance to society, archivists must take as much account as possible of how users wish to search through the archives. Thanks to recent methodological and technological developments, it *can* be done: we can offer users a more intuitive and targeted search experience.

The archival sector has several opportunities to improve and optimise the search experience of users and ensure that it more closely resembles searching on the internet. Those opportunities include advanced search technology, Linked Data and forms of artificial intelligence such as automated text recognition (including Handwritten Text Recognition, HTR) and language models (Large Language Models, LLM). Users are accustomed to Google and full text searching. They want to be able to use filters, to be referred to related information and to reach the information they seek as quickly as possible. Users do not want to pass through numerous layers and click on many links before reaching information, and they do not want to have to attend a training course to understand what is meant by ‘Documents concerning special subjects’ or ‘2012 addition’. In short, they expect to be able to use the usual digital search methods of the 21st century.

In the *Proof of Contexts* (PoC) project, we studied one of the aforementioned opportunities to improve the search experience of users: transforming a hierarchically organised archive inventory into a network structure. The project is a collaboration between the Noord-Holland Archives (NHA, *Noord-Hollands Archief*) and the Amsterdam City Archives (ACA, *Stadsarchief Amsterdam*). We worked with the Norday design agency and our data partner Spinque to develop an alternative design for searching through archival material. In partnership with a group of archivists from archival organisations in the province of Noord-Holland, we studied how we can model metadata differently to facilitate a new way of searching and presenting information by using Records in Contexts, the new archival description standard based on Linked Data. We then presented the design to a group of users.

The objective of the PoC was to design and test an alternative to the traditional inventory to show how it can be done differently. This report consists of a detailed description of the steps taken, the thought processes and the choices we made. Before the PoC can be developed into a specific plan, many details must first be studied and agreed. The PoC is intended to prompt a discussion about these questions and to help the archival sector to work together to take the next steps in the coming years. We encourage everyone to work together, to develop ideas further, to take the next steps and to adopt, develop and publish responses to the recommendations.

The report first considers the ideas and conceptual framework for the metadata modelling. Chapter two describes how the modelling was applied in practice in the PoC and how it can be implemented for all archives using automation. Chapter three discusses the developments during the ‘design week’ with Norday and Spinque, and presents the designs for the prototypes we developed. Chapter four presents the results of the user study. These are followed by a conclusion and the potential next steps, points requiring attention and recommendations.

Happy reading!

Merel Geerlings and Nico Vriend

Chapter 1: The ideas

Helping the Filing Monster

Have you heard of the Filing Monster? The monster appears in one of the many adventures that Andy and Terry experience in the *Treehouse* children's book series.¹ One day, the two friends and their friend Jill arrive on an island filled with stacks of filing cabinets. They go ashore and notice that the island is largely devoid of life: everything has been filed. When they open one of the file drawers, the Filing Monster appears. He is angry, because the three friends have mixed up everything! The monster loves filing, and found this island that needed to be filed. He decides to file Andy, Terry and Jill too, "under M for MEDDLING HUMANS WHO SHOULD MIND THEIR OWN BUSINESS! [...] You're a bunch of *meddling* humans. What else could it *possibly* be?", he asks. The friends propose many other options: under the first letters of their names, for example, or their jobs, or perhaps the colour of their eyes. "'STOP! STOP! STOP!', says the monster. 'You're getting me all confused!' 'Sorry', says Jill. 'We're just trying to help.'"

The Filing Monster. Andy Griffiths and Terry Denton, The 117-Storey Treehouse (Macmillan children's books, London, 2019) 259.

¹ Andy Griffiths and Terry Denton, *The 117-Storey Treehouse* (Macmillan children's books, London, 2019)

With the Filing Monster, the authors of *The 117-Storey Treehouse* present us – probably unintentionally – with a metaphor for the daily archiving practices that have been followed for decades, and certainly in the century following the publication of the globally influential *Manual for the Arrangement and Description of Archives* by Muller, Feith and Fruin in 1898. While these practices are logical, and are possibly the best solution in an analogue world, they have limitations. Because, after all, the Filing Monster can place documents in only one drawer, in one file, under one letter. In today's digital world, that is no longer necessary: you can store documents in several drawers. Just as Terry, Andy and Jill, we must help the Filing Monster, because the archival sector has allowed too many traces of the analogue world to persist in the digital world.

It is logical that the familiar idea of one thing in one place has been retained in the digital world. Consider, for example, Johan Leonard Lang, who can be seen driving on Huidekooperstraat in Amsterdam on 1 June 1899. He has attracted a lot of attention:

Johan Leonard Lang (1869-1952) on his car, a French Décauville, on Huidekooperstraat in Amsterdam adjacent to numbers 25-29, 1899. Jacob Olie, Amsterdam City Archives

The car looks more like a horse drawn coach than a car as we know it today. People were only familiar with coaches, and wanted to mechanise them, which is why the first car resembled a coach. We see the same with archives: the old idea of one document in one file in one place in the filing cabinet. Traditional inventories still contain a description of documents and files in a single place in

the archives. An organisational system, a hierarchical structure, was devised to allow those documents and files to be found quickly. A new series or file is generally created when the number of documents becomes too large and the list becomes too long. This often results in a very deep hierarchical folder structure.

3376 Automobielvereniging De Rijmonders te IJmuiden

- ▶ Kenmerken
- ▶ Inleiding
- ▶ **Inventaris**

Inventaris

- 1. Stukken van algemene aard
- 2. Stukken van bijzondere aard
Toon details van deze beschrijving ▶
 - 2.1. Reglementen
 - 2.2. Organisatie
 - 2.3. Sportcommissie
 - 2.4. Jubileum
 - 2.5. Ledenadministratie
 - 2.6. Financiën
 - 2.7. Verenigingsactiviteiten
 - 2.8. Contacten met andere organisaties
 - 2.9. Documentatie

laatste wijziging 03-06-2020, 261 beschreven archiefstukken

The same is true in the digital world, for example the inventory on the website, or the hierarchical folder structure in *Windows Explorer*. How often have you had to look in multiple files to find or collect the information you were looking for? How often does it happen that a document about a subject also concerns other subjects, which means you have to look for it in a totally different place? As a user, you search through this hierarchical structure and hope you'll eventually find everything, although you can never be sure.

Consider the example on the left: the fonds of 'Automobielvereniging De Rijmonders', a motorists' association in the town of IJmuiden. It has been organised hierarchically. All the metadata can be searched digitally.

However, is metadata still useful with today's records, as we can perform full-text searches on documents? This is inherently possible with 'born digital' archives, and HTR makes it possible to directly search through the data in digitised analogue archives. You can, as it were, run a Google search in the archives – a fantastic development for users. However, that doesn't mean that record metadata will fall out of use, because:

- Not everything you may wish to know about a document is contained in the document itself. For example, the owner of a diary doesn't always write his or her name in the diary. Metadata will always be useful as a means of searching for information.
- Metadata also gives information context. Who created it? What is it about? To which information is something related?
- With full-text searching, metadata is a way of refining (potentially numerous) search results using filters.

That metadata is currently trapped in the traditional, hierarchical archive inventory and is not linked to other information. The challenge is to model that metadata in such a way that it can be accessed using the search techniques that users use online and are familiar with.

The principles of Linked Data can help, as well as Records in Contexts (RiC) as a description standard. The basic principle is that information is not shown hierarchically, but as a network of data. A single document or file can now be linked to other documents and files, as well other entities, such as people or locations. Many business systems and document management systems that contain 'born digital' information objects already work in this way. In these systems, the network structure of RiC works much better than the traditional hierarchical inventory structure.

The coach-like car evolved to become the car as we know it today. With this PoC, we have done the same for archival material.

From tree to network

Many employees of the archival organisations in the province of Noord-Holland (Noord-Holland Archives, Amsterdam City Archives, *Regionaal Archief Alkmaar* (archives of the Alkmaar region), *Archief Gooi en Vechtstreek* (archives of the Gooi en Vecht region), *Westfries Archief* (archives of the Westfriesland region) and *Gemeentearchief Zaanstad* (archives of the municipality of Zaanstad)) came together to study whether, and how, we can actually transform a traditionally structured archive inventory into a network structure. By carrying out various exercises, we identified what accessibility means for archives in the world of Linked Data.

In one of the exercises, the archivists adopted the role of users to discover which elements are most important for them when finding specific records. When thinking from the perspective of the user, metadata such as location, personal, subject and time descriptions were mentioned first, and only later the archive creator. Of course, the archive creator is an essential part of explaining and understanding the context of records, but should it be the primary or even the only way of accessing those records? This is currently the reality in most of our search systems.

Many of the other exercises concerned the organisational structure used by archives: the hierarchical structure. The conclusion was that the strongly hierarchically tree structure of traditional inventories is not a true network of data, but that it can be retrospectively transformed into a network structure. For example, some information currently contained in series names could be better placed elsewhere in the network. This transformation – which is central to the PoC – can be realised by using Linked Data technology and Records in Contexts (RiC) as the description standard.

As the name Records in Contexts suggests, this involves placing pieces of information (records, from documents to images and audio recordings) in a context, whatever that may be. They may be placed in multiple contexts, in fact in all known contexts. To specify how, RiC defines the following entities:

RIC-CM v1.0: a global overview

Created by ICA-EGAD in September 2023.

This diagram is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License.

On the far left, the diagram shows how records (*Record Set*, *Record* and *Record Part*) can be described, and how those records can be linked to context entities such as *Place*, *Date*, *Activity* and various agents, including *Person*, *Family* and *Corporate Body*. All entities are mutually connected by means of relations. Those relations also have specific names, as can be seen in the diagram. This is the Linked Data structure that serves as the foundation for RiC. This is new for archives, because until now each inventory was an isolated phenomenon: the information they contain is rarely connected to other entities.

RiC-E04	Record
Attribute ID	Attribute Name
RiC-A43	General Description
RiC-A22	Identifier
RiC-A28	Name
RiC-A03	Authenticity Note
RiC-A07	Classification
RiC-A08	Conditions of Access
RiC-A09	Conditions of Use
RiC-A10	Content Type
RiC-A21	History
RiC-A24	Integrity Note
RiC-A25	Language
RiC-A26	Legal Status
RiC-A35	Record Resource Extent
RiC-A38	Scope and content
RiC-A39	State
RiC-A40	Structure
RiC-A17	Documentary Form Type

Every entity in RiC has an extensive list of data (called *Attributes* or *Properties*) that you can assign to that entity. The figure on the left shows the information that can be stored about a record, for example: no less than seventeen fields.

Some will already be familiar:

- *Identifier*: reference number
- *Name*: description
- *Record Resource Extent*: outward appearance, which is the quantity of information content, such as two letters.

However, there are many more. For example, you can assign a classification (personnel, finance, etc.) or the document type (*Documentary Form Type*) separately, or the language the document is written in, rather than stating this information textually in the description.

With Records in Contexts in mind, the group of archivists studied all the series names in all archives in the Noord-Holland Archives: around 70,000. The series names proved to

be very diverse, as shown in the figures below. Most of the information in the series names could indeed be better placed elsewhere in the network.

TOEGANGSCOD	CODE	VOLGNUMME	TITEL	DATERING	BEGINJAAR	EINDJAAR
141	2.1.03.	48	Jan van Styrum (1643-1680), gehuwd met Maria Steyr			
141	2.1.09.	74	Jan van Styrum (1721-1774), gehuwd met Anna Maria			
1614	2.1.1.2.2.	471	Jan van Sypesteyn C.A. I zoon (1670-1690)			
1614	2.1.1.2.2.	391	Jan van Sypesteyn en Cornelisz. (1633-1669), Maria v			
141	2.2.22.3.	670	Jan van Vollenhoven Willemszoon, gehuwd met Helen			
3934	6.2.	131	Jan van W. (1759-1837)	1759	1837	
3260	1.2.	18	Jan van Wickevoort Crommelin (1702-1740) en Elisat			
142	1.5.36.1.	6343	Jan Verloren			
1639	7.	925	Jan Voster	1992	1992	
1614	2.1.1.3.12	1608	Jan Willem Druyvesteyn François Constantijnsz. (175			
1614	2.1.1.3.12	1611	Jan Willem Druyvesteyn Jan Willemsz. (1786-1857) en			
936	5.5.	25	Jan Willem Reinier Tilanus (1823-1914)			
186.15	1.	5	Jan Willem Roeloffs Valk			
1604		50	Jan Willem van der Steur (1862-1945), AXh			
1571	1.1.2.15.2	1019	Jannetje van Gilse 1838-1905 en Pieter Hendrik Testa			
3993	1.8.8.2.	10	Jansheren na 1625			
1604		5	Jansje van der Steur, C IX (1833-1903)			
3249	2.1.2.9.	232	Jansje van Zwieten			
1972	25.	2678	Janssen, E 1894-1896	1894	1896	
1073	1.2.14.2.4	367	Jansstraat			
2106	13.2.2.2.1	5	Jansstraat			
2106	15.1.1.1.4	765	Jansstraat			
774	1.5.1.	2	Jansstraat 40			
18	2.2.6.2.	1935	Jansstraat 46, Prinsenhof, hulpegebouw Klein Heiliglan			
18	3.1.2.6.2.	7999	Jansstraat 46, Prinsenhof, hulpegebouw Klein Heiliglan			
5001	25.3.2.14.	17	Jansstraat e.o.			
3945		16	Jansstraat te Haarlem			
1518	3.3.2.	552	Jansstraat, Gemeentearchief			
1518	3.3.16.	1260	Jansstraat, Janskerk met Gemeentearchief			
5010	2.2.2.2.13	65	Jansweg/Parklaan			
1639	23.	974	Jantien de	1998	1998	1998
936	3.8.1.	5	Janus Red	1895	1895	1895
1627	2.6.1.	5	Japan			
2482		9682	Japan			
1627	2.6.	30	Japan, Zuid- en Oost-Azië			

TOEGANGSCOD	CODE	VOLGNUMME	TITEL	DATERING	BEGINJAAR	EINDJAAR
615	7.1.	7504	Resumé of titles of Freudenthal's books, articles, lec			
615	7.1.1.	7508	A			
615	7.1.2.	7569	B			
615	7.1.3.	7631	C			
615	7.1.4.	7671	D			
615	7.1.5.	7718	E			
615	7.1.6.	7782	F			
615	7.1.7.	7811	G			
615	7.1.8.	7869	H			
615	7.1.9.	7926	I			
615	7.1.10.	7998	J			
615	7.1.11.	8003	K			
615	7.1.12.	8058	L			
615	7.1.13.	8128	M			
615	7.1.14.	8203	N			
615	7.1.15.	8252	O			
615	7.1.16.	8323	P			
615	7.1.17.	8373	Q			
615	7.1.18.	8379	R			
615	7.1.19.	8468	S			
615	7.1.20.	8548	T			
615	7.1.21.	8627	U			
615	7.1.22.	8651	V			
615	7.1.23.	8703	W			
615	7.1.24.	8818	Y			
615	7.1.25.	8822	Z			
616	1.	64	Stukken van algemene aard			
616	1.1.	65	Jaarverslagen			
616	2.	79	Stukken van bijzondere aard			
616	2.1.	80	Organisatie en personeel			
616	2.1.1.	81	Organisatie			
616	2.1.2.	112	Financiën			

In general terms, the information in the series names can be categorised into action types:

- Adding information from a series name to a record as an attribute:
 - *Classification*, e.g. employees, finance
 - *Documentary Form Type*, e.g. annual report, minutes
 - *Date*, e.g. year or date

- Adding information from a series name as another entity:
 - Person: all names of persons belong in the *Person* entity and must be described there; a relation can be used to indicate whether the person is or was an archive creator or former, for example
 - Corporate Body: as for persons
 - Location
 - Subjects

There are also series names that are largely meaningless for users, because no one searches for those words or because they do not give the document any context. In the PoC, we ignored the following series names:

- Documents concerning general subjects, documents concerning special subjects
- Other matters, miscellaneous, various
- Documentation
- Documents for which the relationship with the fonds is unclear
- Addition
- Letters (A, B, C, etc.)

Finally, there are series names that can be interpreted in several ways. For example, 'Concertgebouw': it is a building, a location and an organisation. What exactly does the series name mean? Only a more detailed study of the inventory, or the underlying documents themselves, can clarify this.

When the processing actions are carried out, the hierarchical structure is converted without meaning being lost. The result is a flat list of records. The records themselves are described better and are also correctly linked to context entities. Following the conversion, we retain the existing meaning while offering users *more* meaning and contexts. It adds something, rather than taking something away. In chapter three of this report, which discusses the design, we explain why it is so important to model data in this way. In the next chapter, we begin with the implementation of the metadata conversion.

Chapter 2: How? The implementation

In chapter one, we discussed the transformation of the traditional inventory into a network of data in conceptual terms. Although the group of archivists who worked on this were very enthusiastic about the thought process they had followed, one important question remained unanswered: ‘how do we do it in practice?’ In this chapter, we first describe how we manually processed an example fonds, followed by what we now know about the techniques we can use to do so automatically.

Example: starting by hand

To test whether the ideas would work in practice, we searched for a single fonds to use as an example. It needed to meet the following criteria:

- It had to contain various categorisation systems, including ‘documents concerning general subjects’, ‘special subjects’ and ‘deposited archives’
- The number of records had to be not too large or too small
- It had to contain scanned records

We settled on the fonds with reference number 439 in the Amsterdam City Archives: ‘Archief van de Regenten van de Stichting Rooms-Katholiek Burger Oude-mannenhuus’ (Fonds of the Regents of the Roman Catholic Home for Elderly Men Foundation). This fonds concerns subjects that are still relevant today, including elderly care and housing. The main structure of the fonds is shown in the figure on the right. We analysed this structure and processed it by hand based on the ideas developed during the conceptual phase. We used a test environment in the collection management system of the Amsterdam City Archives, into which we copied the records (the items in the fonds) and the information about the fonds. This allowed us to work undisturbed.

1	ALGEMENE ZAKEN
2	BIJZONDERE ZAKEN
2.1	STICHTING EN WIJZE VAN INRICHTING VAN HET HUIS
2.2	REGENTEN
2.3	PERSONEEL
2.4	VERZORGDEN
2.5	VERZORGING
2.6	KAPEL EN GEESTELIJKHEID
2.7	FINANCIEN
2.8	EIGENDOMMEN
3	VARIA
4	AANHANGSEL
4.1	PERSOONLIJK ARCHIEF VAN JOSEPHUS AUGUSTINUS BRENTANO
4.2	PERSOONLIJK ARCHIEF VAN MR. G.J. DE MARTINI

Step 1: remove meaningless intermediate hierarchical levels

It can clearly be seen that this fonds contains series names that are largely meaningless for users. In this case, these are:

- General subjects
- Special subjects
- Miscellaneous
- Annex

We removed these series for the purposes of the practical implementation of the PoC.

Step 2: add information from series names that are categories to the record

Within the hierarchical structure of this fonds, many terms are used that lend themselves to the creation of a classification system, including 'Employees' and 'Finance'. In RiC terms, these are attributes or properties associated with records (rico:Classification). To this end, we created a new field and attached the terms 'as-is' from the series names in the form of a list of choices (see the figure on the right).

This list of choices is used to generate the filtering options presented in the design of the PoC as described in chapter three. There are however limitations to this method. As can be seen in the figure on the right, the quality of the list leaves much to be desired. Terms such as 'holdings' (*eigendommen*) and 'securities' (*effecten*) are of course related to finance, and should ideally be linked to this term by means of a terminology source. This would make the search process more effective and avoids users becoming bogged down in a sea of thousands of different terms. However, there is as yet no good terminology source for classifications or categories. This must be developed to allow all archives to be processed automatically. For the purposes of the exercise, we copied the terms from the series names as they are.

Step 3: identify archive creators and add them to the Person entity

This fonds has two series containing 'annexes', which consist of archival material created by others (see figure below on the left). These materials were collected by two persons, J.A. Brentano and G.J. de Martini, for whom we created the *Person* entity. We related all the records under

that series to the *Person*, and assigned the role of *Archive creator*. The series were then deleted for the purposes of the practical implementation of the PoC.

The result of these three steps is that all information from the series names was either added to records as attributes, or as other entities with relations to records. The result is a flat list of records:

Collecties / Proof of Contexts (267 records)

Verwijderen Voeg toe aan set Voeg toe aan project Bulk Exporteren

+ Toevoegen record Lijst

Media	Samenvatting ↑ ×	Record type
<input type="checkbox"/>	1, Notulen van regenten Begin date: 1841-01-01, End date: 1896-12-31, Resource extent: 1 deel	BestanddeelPoc
<input type="checkbox"/>	2, Notulen van regenten Begin date: 1872-01-01, End date: 1896-12-31, Resource extent: 1 deel	BestanddeelPoc
<input type="checkbox"/>	3, Notulen van regenten Begin date: 1896-01-01, End date: 1923-12-31, Resource extent: 1 deel	BestanddeelPoc
<input type="checkbox"/>	4, Register van uitgaande stukken Begin date: 1841-01-01, End date: 1881-12-31, Resource extent: 1 deel	BestanddeelPoc
<input type="checkbox"/>	5, Register van uitgaande stukken Begin date: 1881-01-01, End date: 1893-12-31, Resource extent: 1 deel	BestanddeelPoc
<input type="checkbox"/>	6, Register van uitgaande stukken Begin date: 1893-01-01, End date: 1928-12-31, Resource extent: 1 deel	BestanddeelPoc
<input type="checkbox"/>	7, Inventaris van het archief, samengesteld door regent P.J.G. Beuns Begin date: 1928-01-01, End date: 1928-12-31, Resource extent: 2 delen	BestanddeelPoc
<input type="checkbox"/>	8, Inventaris van het archief, samengesteld door regent P.J.G. Beuns Begin date: 1928-01-01, End date: 1928-12-31, Resource extent: 2 delen	BestanddeelPoc
<input type="checkbox"/>	9, Korte levensbeschrijving van J.A. Brentano en geschiedenis van het huis, samengesteld door regent P.J.G. Beuns tot 1924 en vervolgd door zijn opvolgers Begin date: 1928-01-01, End date: 1938-12-31, Resource extent: 1 deel	BestanddeelPoc
<input type="checkbox"/>	10, Uittreksel uit het testament van de stichter J.A. Brentano, houdende aanwijzingen voor de wijze van inrichting en de hieromtrent door executeuren te raadplegen juristen Begin date: 1811-01-01, End date: 1811-12-31, Resource extent: 1 omslag	BestanddeelPoc

However, we decided to go a step further in the PoC by adding enriched information at the level of the record descriptions.

Step 4: copy and add information from the record descriptions

The example fonds contains fairly extensive record descriptions. It was relatively straightforward to standardise these:

- The collective descriptions can be eliminated by moving the information in those collective descriptions to the record descriptions.
- The record descriptions contain information that, according to the principles of RiC, can better be placed elsewhere:
 - Many descriptions begin with a document type, such as 'letter'. With RiC, this is a separate attribute of a record. This information can also be standardised by using a

terminology source for document types, although this is yet to be developed. We added an extra field to the records, created a list of choices and linked the information to the records. The list is now a flat list of terms, but should ideally be linked to structured terms, with horizontal and vertical (hierarchical) relationships, as in a SKOS (Simple Knowledge Organisation System) data model.

- The descriptions often contain an address in Amsterdam. We also included that information as an attribute of the records. While locations outside Amsterdam are equally relevant, they were omitted for the purposes of the practical implementation of the PoC.
- The descriptions contain many names of persons and organisations. We created the persons and organisations in question as items and linked them to the records with the relation 'mentioned'.

The figures below show which information is now directly associated with the records following the processing steps. This information is underlined in red.

Identificatie

* Archief 439. Archief van de... 1/1

* Inventarisnummer 134

Beschrijving
Eigendomsbewijzen en andere stukken betreffende Herengracht 544. Sterfhuis van J.A. Brentano

Nota bene
N.B. De beide huizen Herengracht 542 en 544 zijn in het begin der dertiger jaren afgebroken, waarna ter plaatse een verzorgingstehuis voor 30 bejaarde heren is gebouwd

Datum (tekst) 1677 t/m 1934

Begindatum 01 januari 1677

Einddatum 31 december 1934

Categorie Eigendommen Onroerende goede...
toevoegen link 2/100

Documenttype Eigendomsbewijs toevoegen link 1/100

Uiterlijke vorm 40 stukken

Naam van straat Herengracht 1/1

Huisnummer van 544

Huisnummer tot

Rol actor vormer 1/1

Actor Stichting Rooms-Ka... 1/1

Rol actor vermelde 1/1

Actor Brentano, Josephus... 1/1

In the future: automated

In the future, can we automate the steps that we carried out by hand? A group of technical experts was asked to answer this question: Rick Comanje, Mark Lindeman, Antoinet Nijssen, Niek Verhoeff and Ivo Zandhuis. A brainstorming session resulted in the conclusion that a fairly unambiguous – and relatively obvious, in the opinion of the experts – step-by-step plan can be proposed:

1. The data model and the terminology sources are ready. A terminology source must still be developed for the classifications or categories and document types. The same applies to agents (persons, families, organisations and organisational units).
2. You export the metadata for each record, including the path name (fonds→series→description) of the hierarchical structure. You store this.
3. You apply keyword extraction to the exported data by passing the entire path name of the records through a language model. You ask the model to generate a list of the most common terms. This list is used not just to generate the filtering options, but also to enrich the keywords.
4. You can enrich the keywords by linking them to:
 - a. Terminology sources for classifications or categories, document types, etc.
 - b. Other entities (such as persons, archive creators and organisational units) in your data model. If the entity does not exist, you can create and link a new entity.

Named Entity Recognition and Named Entity Linking technologies are needed for this step. Open tools such as OpenRefine can help. Proficiency in the Python programming language and SPARQL query language is also useful.

The expert group stated that a step-by-step approach is possible: entity by entity, enriching and standardising where possible. For example, you can begin with an easy entity such as persons, as these are relatively straightforward to identify, before moving on to document types. This means it is unnecessary to immediately radically alter the traditional archive inventory as we know it. In the PoC, we did however do so for experimental purposes. Making better use of the network by adding data complements the tree structure of the traditional archive inventory. The classifications or categories can be provided in an enriched form alongside the hierarchical structure. The hierarchical tree remains as one of the search options for users, but we also make it possible to access other entities and attributes in the network. However, we expect that users will make less and less use of the tree structure as the records are gradually enriched. Although the tree may not disappear, it will become less and less relevant.

Chapter 3: The design

Developing new search methods and data models at the conceptual level is one thing; actually creating a new search interface for users is another matter. For this phase, we sought the assistance of the Norday design agency and our technical partner Spinque. We again adopted the role of the user to discover how users want to search the archive and see the results of their search query.

The route

To develop a high-quality design in partnership with Norday and Spinque, we began by defining the problem and the scope of the PoC. This process involved various 'expert talks', in which NHA and ACA employees explained how archives work and the potential accessibility improvements. The PoC focused on presenting records in a new and different way: can we create an attractive and self-explanatory design?

We sketched out our ideas together. What should a fonds page look like (i.e. the page describing the fonds, where you generally see an introduction and inventory at present)? What should the detail page for records look like?

We analysed all the designs and the participants voted for the proposals that impressed them the most. The result was used to develop the visual prototype.

The design is based on the presentation of a single, specific fonds: the example fonds from the previous chapter. The search steps taken to reach that specific fonds were not considered. The manually processed dataset was sent to Spinque, where it was analysed and the possibilities identified.

A wall covered with sketches, with yellow dots to vote for favourite elements

The prototypes

Two prototypes were made: a visual design and a technical design. The visual design can be viewed here: [SAA-NHA Design Prototype - Design](#). It is based on data we created for the PoC, but is not a functional website. In other words, the data cannot be queried live. To allow this, Spinque also created a technical prototype so we could test whether the modifications to the metadata also result in a better search experience. The visual prototype consists of designs for the pages for a fonds, an extensive record and a simple record.

The design for the fonds as a whole starts with the title and introduction to the fonds. This is followed by a search bar, followed by two tabs: 'Overzicht' (Summary) and 'Archiefstukken' (Records):

Archief: Regenten van de Stichting Rooms-Katholiek Burger Oude-mannenhuis

Josephus Augustinus Brentano, geboren in 1753 in Amsterdam, stierf in 1821 en liet een groot fortuin na voor de oprichting van "Brentano's Sticht des Oudendoms", een instelling voor de verzorging van oudere katholieke mannen. Zijn testament bepaalde dat minimaal 12 mannen huisvesting en zorg zouden krijgen in een speciaal gebouw. De executeurs, onder wie Paulus Anthony Nicolaï, kozen in...

ARCHIEF DOCUMENTEN
439 266

Op de kaart is 01-03 het voormalige Burger Oude-mannenhuis van Stichting Brentano's Sticht des Oudendoms.

Overzicht Archiefstukken

Wat zit er in het archief?

Eigendommen 111
 Legaten & Erfinstellingen 27
 Financien 51
 Onroerende goederen 44
 Advertenties en publicaties 22
 Personeel 12
 Verzorgden 11
 Regentes 0
 Verzorging 5
 Stichting en wijze inst... 5
 Effecten 5
 Kapel en geestelijkheid 5
 Hypotheek 2
 Opfas met ifreemclausule 2
 Roerende goederen 1

Meest geraadpleegd

- REGISTER**
Register van verzorgden, Chronologisch
1813 - 1861 - 19137
- BOEKJE**
Korte levensbeschrijving van J.A. Brentano en geschiedenis van het huis, samengesteld door regent P.J.G. Beuns tot 1924 en vervolgd door zijn opvolgers
1823 - 1924 - 11915
- REGLEMENTEN**
Reglementen voor de verzorgden
1776 - 1784 - 17975
- Stukken betreffende medische verzorging
184 - 182 - 11942

Personen

- Josephus Augustinus Brentano**
1753 - 1821
- Carel Thomas Brentano**
1753 - 1821
- G.J. Martini**
1733 - 1821

Op de kaart

Archiefstructuur

- 1 Algemene zaken
- 2 Bijzondere zaken
- 3 Varia
- 4 Aa-hangsel

Gerelateerde archieven

- Archief van het Sint-Janshof, Leproziehuis en Oude Mannen- en Vrouwen-gasthuis
- Archief van het Rooms-Katholiek Oude-Armenkantoor en R.K. Bejaardenhuis Sint Jacob

Archief: Regenten van de Stichting Rooms-Katholiek Burger Oude-mannenhuis

Josephus Augustinus Brentano, geboren in 1753 in Amsterdam, stierf in 1821 en liet een groot fortuin na voor de oprichting van "Brentano's Sticht des Oudendoms", een instelling voor de verzorging van oudere katholieke mannen. Zijn testament bepaalde dat minimaal 12 mannen huisvesting en zorg zouden krijgen in een speciaal gebouw. De executeurs, onder wie Paulus Anthony Nicolaï, kozen in...

ARCHIEF DOCUMENTEN
439 266

Op de kaart is 01-03 het voormalige Burger Oude-mannenhuis van Stichting Brentano's Sticht des Oudendoms.

Overzicht Archiefstukken

266 RESULTATEN

Document type

- Eigendomsbewijs (37)
- Advertentie / publicatie (23)
- Brief (14)
- Kladkaasboek (13)
- Testamenteire beschikking (13)
- Kaasboek (12)
- Journal (11)
- Grootboek (9)

Categorie

- Eigendommen (113)
- Legaten en erfinstellingen (37)
- Financien (51)
- Onroerende goederen (44)
- Advertenties en publ... (22)
- Personeel (12)
- Verzorgden (11)
- Regenten (0)
- Verzorging (5)

Datering

van tot

Person of Organisatie

CONCEPTINSTRUCTIE
Concept-instructie voor de binnen-vader, met begeleidende brief van notaris mr. J.P. van Etten
1872 - 21
Personeel

INVENTARIS
Inventaris van het archief, samengesteld door regent P.J.G. Beuns
1788 - 1892 - 7
Eigendommen

BOEKJE
Korte levensbeschrijving van J.A. Brentano en geschiedenis van het huis, samengesteld door regent P.J.G. Beuns tot 1924 en vervolgd door zijn opvolgers
1677 - 1876 - 47
Verzorging

BRIEF
Sollicitatiebrief van portier W. Schouten
1822 - 32
Personeel

GROOTBOEK
Grootboek
1805 - 1823 - 29187
Financien

AKTE
Akte van depot voor codicil
1829 - 29170
Legaten En Erfinstellingen Eigendommen

Stukken betreffende door verzorgden mee te brengen en aan hen te verstrekken kleding en Innengoed
1825 - 1924 - 29164
Verzorging

Stukken betreffende medische verzorging
1810 - 1913 - 29166
Legaten En Erfinstellingen Eigendommen

Figure left: 'Overzicht' tab.
Figure right: 'Archiefstukken' tab.

The 'Overzicht' tab starts with a dashboard containing information about the contents of the fonds. This is intended for users who wish to familiarise themselves with the contents of the fonds. The dashboard contains the following elements:

- 'Wat zit er in het archief?' (*What does the fonds contain?*) This includes a pie chart made up of the categories assigned to the records in the fonds. This allows you to see all the subjects that the records refer to at a glance. It is intended to give users a general idea of the contents of the fonds.
- 'Meest geraadpleegd' (*Most frequently consulted*). For many archives, we have a clear idea which records people search for most often. For many people, this is a useful shortcut to the record they are looking for. It also gives an impression of what can be found in the fonds.
- 'Personen' (*Persons*). Archives often concern people. We can show which persons are linked to a specific fonds. You can choose to search for records that refer to those persons.
- 'Op de kaart' (*On the map*). Some archives have a strong geographical component. In this case, it can be useful to search on the map.
- 'Archiefstructuur' (*Archival structure*). As explained in chapter two, the traditional inventory can still be presented as a search method, alongside other views. Users who wish to consult the inventory can do so here.
- 'Gerelateerde archieven' (*Related archives*). Here you can show any related archives and give the user a hint to look there. For example, some archive creators have multiple fonds.

The information in the dashboard is generated automatically and is data-driven as much as possible. For example, the most frequently consulted records can be identified from statistical data, and the pie chart can be generated using data about the number of reference numbers (or possibly scans) per category. An important benefit of this data-driven approach is that it can also be implemented in practice. After all, it is impractical to generate these summaries by hand for thousands of different archives, although it is always possible to allow the option of making manual adjustments.

The data-driven approach has even more benefits, based on the principles of Linked Data. The data sources to which links are made, such as a terminology source for classifications or categories or the reconstruction of persons, contain numerous items of enriched data that can be shown here. In our example, years of birth and death and professions are given for the persons shown – data sourced from Wikidata – or an explanatory text if you click on one of the categories in the pie chart. This information could be fetched from the (yet to be developed) terminology source. One of the major benefits of this approach is that you only need to store data in a single place, i.e. the terminology source, to show, reuse and extract value from it in multiple places.

Pie chart after clicking on one of the categories

However, the data-driven approach has a disadvantage, as the dashboard can only be constructed based on the metadata available at present. This means it can give a distorted impression of reality, for example if underrepresented groups or unidentified persons are missing in summaries of this type. To make users more aware of this problem, an explanation of the origin of the data can be shown for any desired element. In the design, this can be seen in the form of an ‘i’ (with hover-over) after the section title *What does the fonds contain?*

The ‘Archiefstukken’ (Records) tab shows a summary of all the records in the example fonds. A technical prototype was created to allow the operation of the design to be assessed effectively. This is shown below:

Archief van de Regenten van de Stichting Rooms-Katholiek Burger Oude-mannenhuus

Inleiding. Ontstaan en geschiedenis tot 1924. Op maandag 16 april 1821 overleed, in zijn woning aan de Herengracht ten oosten van de Reguliersgracht te Amsterdam (later genummerd: 544), Josephus Augustinus Brentano. Brentano, die op 28 augustus 1753 te Amsterdam werd geboren en op diezelfde dag in de kerk 'Mozes en Aäron' werd gedoopt, en die dus ruim 67 jaar oud werd, bleef zijn leven lang ongehuwd. Bij testament, op 27 februari 1811 t.o.v. notaris mr. Johan Reinier van der Gronden te Amsterdam verleden, bevestigd bij testament op 4 april 1821 voor diezelfde notaris gepasseerd, bestemde Brentano zijn gehele nalatenschap, ter waarde van een paar honderdduizend gulden, na aftrek van enkele legaten, die tot enige tienduizende guldens beperkt bleven.;

[lees meer](#) ▾

🔍

FILTER

Periode

Start jaar Eind jaar →

Document Type

- Eigendomsbewijs 37
- Advertentie/publicatie 23
- Brief 14
- Kladkasboek 13
- Testamentaire beschikk... 13
- Kasboek 12

Categorie

- Eigendommen 111
- Legaten en erfstellingen 57
- Financiën 51
- Onroerende goederen 44
- Advertenties en publica... 23
- Personeel 12

Person en Organisatie

- Martini, de, G.J. 27
- Brentano, Josephus Au... 21
- Brentano, Carel Thomas 5
- Nicolai, P.A. 5
- De Amstelbode 4
- Etten, van, Johannes Pet... 3

266 RESULT(S) Relevantie ▾

CONCEPTINSTRUCTIE

Concept-instructie voor de binnen-vader, met begeleidende brief van notaris mr. J.P. van Etten

1872 • Record 21

PERSONEEL

Etten, van, Johannes Petrus

INVENTARIS

Inventaris van het archief, samengesteld door regent P.J.G. Beuns

1928 • Record 7

Stukken betreffende het gemeenschappelijke graf voor en betreffende het begraven van verzorgden

1844 t/m 1929 • Record 47

VERZORGING

REGISTER VAN VERZORGDENREGISTER

Register van kandidaten en verzorgden, chronologisch

1858 t/m 1894 • Record 37

VERZORGDEN

BRIEF

Brief van H.J. van der Burgh, pr., betreffende het schilderen van het portret van zijn vader, wijlen G.J. van der Burgh, oud-regent

1880 • Record 18

REGENTEN

Burgh, van der, G.J. Burgh, van der, H.J.

The records, or the results of a search of the records, can be seen on the right. One or more search terms can be entered in the search bar above. As soon as you start typing, several suggested search queries are generated based on the available data (autofill). You can also combine a search query with filters, as shown on the left, in a similar manner to searching in an online store. In the prototype, a figure after each term shows the number of instances of the term. The filter terms are updated automatically when combined with other filters or search terms. In the prototype, the terms are always sorted by number, with the most frequently occurring first. Of course, other ordering methods are possible, including relevance based on assigning a predetermined 'weighting' to (the location) of particular terms.

The filter options are mostly derived from the metadata processing actions described in the previous chapter. As can be seen, there are only records, no hierarchical tree or series names. All information is shown directly next to the record or context entities such as 'Person'. Because we have created *document type* and *category* as terminology sources and linked them to the records, you can also use them as filters. The same applies to the dates and names of persons and organisations.

With these options, it is easier to perform wider search queries, such as "show me all records related to P.A. Nicolai" or "show me all letters ('brieven') dated between 1800 and 1850". The latter search query is illustrated in the example below:

ARCHIEF 439
 Archief van de Regenten van de Stichting Rooms-Katholiek Burger Oude-mannenhuis

Inleiding. Ontstaan en geschiedenis tot 1924. Op maandag 16 april 1821 overleed, in zijn woning aan de Herengracht ten oosten van de Reguliersgracht te Amsterdam (later genummerd: 544), Josephus Augustinus Brentano. Brentano, die op 28 augustus 1753 te Amsterdam werd geboren en op diezelfde dag in de kerk 'Mozes en Aäron' werd gedoopt, en die dus ruim 67 jaar oud werd, bleef zijn leven lang ongehuwd. Bij testament, op 27 februari 1811 t.o.v. notaris mr. Johan Reinier van der Gronden te Amsterdam verleden, bevestigd bij testament op 4 april 1821 voor diezelfde notaris gepasseerd, bestemde Brentano zijn gehele nalatenschap, ter waarde van een paar honderdduizend gulden, na aftrek van enkele legaten, die tot enige tienduizende guldens beperkt bleven. lees meer ▾

Zoek in dit archief 🔍

FILTER 3 RESULT(S) Relevantie ▾

Periode
 Start jaar 1800 Eind jaar 1850 →

Document Type

- LUGTUI 3
- Uitnodiging 3
- Brief 3
- Veiligscatalogus 2
- Testament 2
- Kasboek 2
- Akte van dépot voor oodl... 2

Categorie

- Stichting en wijze inrichting ... 2
- Verzorgden 1

Person en Organisatie

- Schimmelpennink, J. 2
- Nicolai, P.A. 2
- Toe Laer, Rutger Jan 1
- Brentano, Josephus Augusti... 1
- Vaillant, C.J. 1
- Meijlink, J.C. 1

BRIEF
 Brief, houdende advies van mr. J. Schimmelpennink aan executeur P.A. Nicolai, over het benoemen van regenten en over hun werkzaamheden
 1825 • Record 13

STICHTING EN WIJZE INRICHTING VAN HET HUIS

Schimmelpennink, J. Nicolai, P.A.

BRIEF
 Brief aan P.A. Nicolai, als executeur van J.A. Brentano, houdende advies hoe 't best te handelen in de geest van testateur, uitgebracht door de juristen J. Schimmelpennink, R.J. toe Laer en C.J. Vaillant
 1821 • Record 11

STICHTING EN WIJZE INRICHTING VAN HET HUIS

Nicolai, P.A. Vaillant, C.J. Toe Laer, Rutger Jan Schimmelpennink, J. Brentano, Josephus Augustinus, 1753, 1821

BRIEF
 1841 • Record 42

VERZORGDEN

Meijlink, J.C.

To answer this question using the existing inventory, the user would have to read through all the series to identify the letters. It is often possible to search on existing websites of archival organisations using keywords and dates. However, the results are shown *in* the tree structure. The records may be shown far apart, which means you need to spend a lot of time scrolling and clicking. This is already quite a task with 266 records, let alone with a fonds containing thousands of

descriptions. In our prototype, you see all records at a glance, which also makes it easier to compare them.

For now, we have done so for a single example fonds. But just imagine it was possible to search the entire archives in this way. You could easily enter a search query such as:

- Show me all records in the 'finance' category from fonds X, Y and Z
- Show me all records containing the word 'diamond' in the description, and 'Jodenbreestraat' for the street
- Show me all records from archives of the municipal police in the Netherlands with document type 'day and night report' dated between 1940-1945

This would allow users to search in a more data-oriented way, based on the attributes of the records, and not only using search keywords. Users would no longer need to search through individual inventories to find records. Instead, they could see search results from all inventories of an archival organisation (or even from multiple organisations) at once. The origin of a record (i.e. the fonds it is part of) becomes contextual information, but is no longer the only way of searching for records.

ProofOfContexts / een prototype van Stadsarchief Amsterdam & Noord-Hollands Archief

EIGENDOMSBEWIJS

1677 — 1934

Eigendomsbewijzen en andere stukken betreffende Herengracht 544, Sterfhuys van J.A. Brentano

Herengracht 544, Sterfhuys van J.A. Brentano
 Lees meer ▾

PDF Aanvragen

ARCHIEF SCANS CATEGORIE
 439-134 97 [Eigendommen, Onroerende goederen](#)

Op de kaart Meer over deze locatie →

Person

Josephus Augustinus Brentano
 1753 — 1821
 Kunstverzamelaar

Bekijk persoon →

Gerelateerde beelden Meer over deze locatie →

Wie hebben op deze locatie gewoond? *Uit bevolkingsregister 1874-93

Ida Joannetta Graaf Geboren: 25-04-1847	Zwaantje Werff Geboren: 02-12-1844	Anna Catharina Blom Geboren: 08-07-1847
Cornelia Petronella v den Burg Geboren: 27-10-1849	Sophia Wilhelmina v der Hoek Geboren: 04-06-1835	Trjntje Pos Geboren: 31-09-1857

Bekijk alle bewoners ▾

ARCHIEF - 439

Regenten van de Stichting Rooms-Katholiek Burger Oude-mannenhuys

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Meer over dit archief →

Archiefstructuur Bekijk boomstructuur →

- 2 Bijzondere zaken
 - 2.8 Eigendommen
 - 2.8.3 Onroerende goederen
 - 114-148 Eigendomsbewijzen en andere stukken betreffende huizen

Gerelateerde stukken

EIGENDOMSBEWIJS Register van verzorgden, Onder hun nummer 1 tot 51 1875 — 1840 INV24	EIGENDOMSBEWIJS Register van verzorgden, Onder hun nummer 1 tot 55 1840 — 1858 INV35
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noord-hollands archief

ProofOfContexts / een prototype van Stadsarchief Amsterdam & Noord-Hollands Archief

REGISTER

1825 — 1861

Register van verzorgden, Chronologisch

PDF Aanvragen

ARCHIEF SCANS CATEGORIE
 439-33 16 [Verzorgden](#)

ARCHIEF - 439

Regenten van de Stichting Rooms-Katholiek Burger Oude-mannenhuys

>Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet consectetur. Diam lectus faucibus orci et enim consectetur. Odio sit sed ultrices id adipiscing. Pharetra ullamcorper sem euismod sed orci eu lectus. Aliquam faucibus velit gravida bibendum integer ultrices eu nulla congue. Viverra pharetra auctor ullamcorper risus hendrerit porttitor vestibulum magna pulvinar. Nulla porta ultrices enim commodo nullam. Feugiat urna integer aliquam ultrices. At at consequat cursus in sagittis nulla. Proin quam adipiscing est enim dictum in arcu orci.

Meer over dit archief →

Archiefstructuur Bekijk boomstructuur →

- 2 Bijzondere zaken
 - 2.4 Verzorgden
 - 33-36 Registers van verzorgden

Gerelateerde stukken

REGISTER Register van verzorgden, Onder hun nummer van 1 tot 51 1834 — 1840 INV27	REGISTER Register van verzorgden, Onder hun nummer van 1 tot 55 1840 — 1858 INV35
--	--

noord-hollands archief

On the left is an example of a record with extensive information, on the right is a simpler example

What are users shown on the detail page for a record? This depends on how much metadata is available. This can clearly be seen in the figures: the example on the left is described extensively, with persons and locations, while the example on the right contains only a minimal description. The designs of the record detail pages show that it is very important to show context alongside records. Which fonds are they part of? Which records are related to them (including sequential records, or records from other fonds)? Are entities within the records indexed? This information allows users who reach this page by performing a search query to

immediately interpret the record correctly, without the need to read through the entire tree structure. Users can still see the 'breadcrumb trail' of the original inventory (see the *Archival structure* in the design).

Chapter 4: The responses

What do users think about the ideas and designs for the prototypes? Initial responses were gathered at three moments: during an interim presentation of the design to the archivists of archival organisations in the province of Noord-Holland who took part in the conceptual sessions, during an interim presentation to the board members of the Noord-Holland Archivists' Circle (*Kring van Noord-Hollandse Archivarissen*) and by way of a study with end users of archives.

The proof is in the eating of the pudding. Training of naval stewards responsible for serving crew members, 25 October 1958. De Boer press photo agency, Noord-Holland Archives

Interim presentation to archivists from the province of Noord-Holland

Following the design week with Norday and Spingue, the designs were presented to the participants in the conceptual sessions, i.e. the group of archivists from the province of Noord-Holland. They were enthusiastic about the design. While there are certainly still unanswered questions, these concern the next steps, the realisation of the design, and what else can be done to improve the accessibility of the archives. There appears to be broad acceptance of the design itself. A few responses from participants in the conceptual sessions:

- “It’s pioneering, inspiring and also useful for other archival organisations” - Jeltsje Stobbe, *Regionaal Archief Alkmaar* (archives of the Alkmaar region)
- “The result is great, and I see it as a good starting point for development” - Olga Minkema, *Archief Gooi en Vechtstreek* (archives of the Gooi en Vecht region)

Interim presentation to the members of the Noord-Holland Archivists’ Circle

The interim presentation was also shared with the board of the Noord-Holland Archivists’ Circle. Just as their employees, the board members were enthusiastic about the design. This discussion also primarily concerned the next steps and further research. The board members emphasised that this solution does not depend on a particular software supplier.

User study

Of course it’s great that we as organisers and the participants in the work sessions are enthusiastic, but in the end, ‘the proof is in the eating of the pudding.’ We therefore invited five people to take part in a user study carried out by Norday. The group included experienced and novice researchers, both professional and amateur, who had previous experience with archive websites. This allowed them to compare the old and new ways of searching.

The designs were presented to the participants during the user study. They were asked to describe aloud what they saw, what they expected to happen when they clicked on something, and to perform a search query using both the existing search interface and the new prototype.

According to Norday, the most important conclusions are:

The new way of searching shows results quickly

Despite the fact that people are used to browsing through archives using a tree structure, the participants soon got to grips with the new way of searching and filtering. They could easily find the right results.

- “Actually it’s very logical, because you can see the type of document you’re looking for at the side”

The old way of searching isn’t intuitive and is very slow

With the new way of searching, everyone was able to find the right document. It was a different story with the old, existing interface; two of the five respondents were unable to trace exactly the same document. Those who were able to find it took much longer than in the new system. The participants opened the wrong files, tried search terms that didn’t work, or even resorted to using the search feature in their browser.

- “You actually have to open everything and read through it all to see exactly what’s there. That takes a lot of time, but I’m used to it, because most archives work like that”
- “Yes, I found it [the existing website with a hierarchical tree structure] much more difficult. I had to use *Ctrl-F* to find title deeds. In the previous environment [the new prototypes] it was easy to filter on ‘title deed’”

The old tree structure is sometimes missed

Most respondents didn't miss the old hierarchical tree structure in the new design, although some indicated that the files help to give a feeling of completeness and context. One respondent wondered if, with the new design, she had seen everything in a file. The need for context could be addressed with proper tagging and by clearly showing related records on the detail page (such as 'Other title deeds').

The dashboard is impressive and provides a useful summary

The respondents found the dashboard shown on the 'Overzicht' (Summary) tab in the visual design attractive and said it provides a useful summary if you're not exactly sure what you're looking for.

The respondents were enthusiastic about the enriched records

All respondents were enthusiastic about all the click-through options and the related content on the record detail pages. They were positively surprised by this feature, which made the researchers curious about further possibilities. The ability to include a map view and to show other residents of a location were particularly well received.

- "I think it's great, because you can see exactly where the house was on a cadastral map. (...) And you can see more related photos and everyone who lived there"
- "There must be many other studies that can be linked to it"

In conclusion, Norday stated that: "The respondents were very enthusiastic about the new searching and filtering options. They indicated that they immediately warmed to the new design and could find what they were looking for quicker. It would appear that the old tree structure can be discarded, provided that a feeling of context and completeness can be retained. This can be addressed with clearly differentiable filters on the search page and specific related records on detail pages. The visual summary and the enrichment of records with maps and persons were also greatly appreciated and can help researchers continue their work."

Conclusion and next steps

The goal of the Proof of Contexts has been achieved: we used an example to show that the traditional inventory can indeed be transformed into a network of data. The design was also positively received by both archivists and end users: it appears to offer a more intuitive and targeted search experience. The underlying design and the metadata processing are an example of how the transition could be implemented in practice. The next steps consist of further discussion and brainstorming, research and developing specific plans. The long-term goal is to present not just an example of funds to users in an intuitive and targeted way, but all our archival material.

Next steps

There are specific steps that can be taken to take the ideas further. It isn't necessary to do everything at once; indeed, that would be inadvisable given the scale of the task. It would help to prepare a step-by-step plan to prioritise, experiment, learn and adjust course as necessary. This would also help us understand the required investment in resources and people. Three specific steps can now be taken:

1. Launch a pilot to test the required automation technology

The metadata processing was carried out by hand in this case, but can it be partially automated? A possible method based on keyword extraction and enriching terms was presented in chapter two. Will this method also work in practice?

There are several other issues to be addressed:

- Some records do not have a category, because they are contained in fonds that are not subdivided into series. This is the case for smaller fonds, for which no hierarchical structure exists. How big a problem is this in the search environment? Can a category be assigned to those records based on the information in the description?
- Studying the list of 70,000 series names in the NHA revealed that there are many, many possible categories. These can be adopted as-is, and linked to more generic categories later. The two labels can coexist: the generic category for use as a filter and the specific category as a tag, so that no information is lost. Further research is needed to determine how this will work in practice.

2. Development of terminology sources

Terminology sources are needed to enrich the records. They are currently missing for document types, categories or classifications, roles of actors and organisation types. The archival sector should preferably develop and manage these terminology sources jointly, to facilitate true interoperability and allow users to search through multiple fonds and collections.

3. Launch a pilot with multiple fonds

The prototypes were created for a single fonds, that of the Oude-Mannenhuis in Amsterdam. We specifically chose a relatively small fonds. But would this way of searching also work for multiple fonds, and would the same conclusions apply? What would the search screen look like if users could

search through several fonds simultaneously? How can we make sure the results are still easy to understand?

For example, a pilot could be launched with the municipal police archives held by various archival organisations in the province of Noord-Holland. These archives are not only very similar in terms of their scale and structure, but are also heavily used. In short, a significant increase in value for users can be expected with the new system.

Points requiring attention

In addition to the specific steps described above, there are several points that require attention and recommendations.

Adapting data models

Before organisations can implement these changes, they must first adapt their data models, as new entities and attributes will be added and information will be moved, copied and added.

Data-driven dashboards

Dashboards were created in the prototype to present a clear overview of the search results. These were automated and data-driven as much as possible. As described in chapter three, there is however a disadvantage, because the dashboard can only be built using the currently available data. There are large gaps in the data coverage. For example, if you wish to show which records are viewed most frequently, that data must be available.

Expanding perspectives

Archives include 'silences': records are missing and descriptions were written from the perspective of the archive creator. Adding other perspectives offers new ways of accessing records.

Collective descriptions and indices

Some records have a direct relationship to other records, for example through collective descriptions or indices. Although navigation between these records was not considered in the prototype, the user study revealed that users would appreciate this ability.

Explaining jargon

Jargon is used in many places on archive websites. Aside from the fact that it can often be avoided, existing jargon can also be clarified by explaining terms where they occur. This was done in a few places in the prototype by adding an 'i' icon and showing the meaning as a hover-over. Terminology sources can assist here.

Newly acquired archives

The PoC primarily concerned the processing of 'legacy' metadata from archival organisations and fonds that have existed for decades. However, new archival material is created and acquired all the time. Working instructions must be written for the inclusion of new archival material for which an inventory is prepared, so that this process can take account of the latest developments from the start.

Generating and enriching metadata

The PoC shows that the quality of the metadata is extremely important, but that the metadata we want to see is not always available. Consider the design of the record with minimal data. You can't show, add or standardise metadata that you don't have. The creation of searchable data can be greatly accelerated by scanning analogue records, transcribing them using HTR or OCR, and subsequently extracting, standardising and linking the entities. An integrated approach is needed to optimise the digital accessibility of archival and cultural heritage information.

Offer solutions if there are no search results

What do users see if a search query does not provide any results? While this question was out of scope during the implementation of the PoC, it was asked by many of those involved. The search experience can be improved if users are shown suggestions based on the search term, for example the names of particular fonds that they can view. This can be done by performing a search term analysis of the search environment, extracting categories and adding them to the fonds as tags.

Making natural language search queries possible

Experiments with searching using natural language have been performed. These work in a similar way to chatbots, which can also be trained using the contents of records. This feature can be used to extend a more traditional search environment.

With our thanks to

Proof of Contexts was possible thanks to the efforts of many parties and persons. We would like to express our sincere thanks to:

- The management teams of the Noord-Holland Archives (*Noord-Hollands Archief*) and the Amsterdam City Archives (*Stadsarchief Amsterdam*)
- Noord-Holland Archivists' Circle (*Kring van Noord-Hollandse Archivarissen*)
- Norday
 - Brenda Leensvaart
 - Jacco Ouwerkerk
 - Jasper van der Kamp
 - Tessa Verbij
 - Mischa Heesakkers
 - Jules Verdijk
- Spinqe
 - Michiel Hildebrand
- Participants in conceptual sessions
 - Frederiek ten Broeke (*Regionaal Archief Alkmaar* - archives of the Alkmaar region)
 - Jeltsje Stobbe (*Regionaal Archief Alkmaar* - archives of the Alkmaar region)
 - Olga Minkema (*Archief Gooi en Vechtstreek* - archives of the Gooi en Vecht region)
 - Charl Barel (*Archief Gooi en Vechtstreek* - archives of the Gooi en Vecht region)
 - Anouk Schoemaker (*Westfries Archief* - archives of the Westfriesland region)
 - Mitchell Helant Muller (*Westfries Archief* - archives of the Westfriesland region)
 - Emmie Snijders (*Gemeentearchief Zaanstad* - archives of the municipality of Zaanstad)
 - Antoinet Nijssen (Noord-Holland Archives)
 - Harco Gorter (Noord-Holland Archives)
 - Naomi Verlaan (Noord-Holland Archives)
 - Milan Groot (Noord-Holland Archives)
 - Mirjam Schaap (Amsterdam City Archives)
 - Anne-Marie Kwakernaak (Amsterdam City Archives)
 - Eric Heijselaar (Amsterdam City Archives)
 - Niek Verhoeff (Amsterdam City Archives)
 - Ilse Rombout (Amsterdam City Archives)
 - Jaap Hoogteijling (Amsterdam City Archives)
 - Herbert Jonker (Amsterdam City Archives)
- Participants in technical session
 - Rick Companje (independent and *Het Utrechts Archief* - The Utrecht Archives)
 - Mark Lindeman (independent)
 - Antoinet Nijssen (Noord-Holland Archives)
 - Niek Verhoeff (Amsterdam City Archives)
 - Ivo Zandhuis (independent)
- Participants in user study: Batuhan, Claudia, Machteld, Christine and Marc
- Editing and text correction: Liesbeth Oskamp
- English translation: Taalcentrum VU

Photo report

Conceptual sessions, 3 and 10 June 2024

Technical session, 2 September 2024

Design week and interim presentation, 9-16 September 2024

